

Twelve Python Programs to Help Readers Test Peculiar Properties of Integer Tetration

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Abstract. We present a collection of Python programs designed to facilitate independent testing of some distinctive properties of integer tetration that we have discovered in recent years. These include the constancy of congruence speed and its general formula for any tetration base a not a multiple of 10, as well as the modular recurrences that characterize the phase shift of the rightmost non-stable digit of any such base at height b , for each unit increment of the hyperexponent b . Through twelve sample codes, readers can directly observe and verify the stability patterns and phase shift modularity exhibited by radix-10 tetration. This preprint serves as a practical supplement for independently verifying our published results in number theory.

1. Introduction

In this preprint, we present a collection of Python codes designed to enhance understanding of tetration's peculiar mathematical properties [1], with a particular focus on congruence speed and (asymptotic/modular) phase shifts for various bases [1, 3–7]. These codes provide computational tools to verify the theorems and corollaries established in our prior work. Specifically, we investigate the constancy of congruence speed for tetration bases not divisible by 10 and the modular recurrence (phase shift) observed in the rightmost non-stable digits at successive hyperexponent heights.

The programs were developed collaboratively, with initial drafts supported by OpenAI's language model, ChatGPT. We refined these drafts to incorporate formulae and proofs from our earlier publications, ensuring consistency with the theoretical results. For example, Program XII applies the compact formula from [8] and performs a direct verification by calculating the constant congruence speed using Equation (3) from [5].

This preprint includes twelve code samples that reproduce and extend the main findings of our research, allowing readers to observe how congruence speed remains stable across different bases under tetration operations. Additionally, we provide codes addressing cases where the tetration base is a multiple of 10 (scenarios where the congruence speed of tetration cannot ever stabilize [6]), thereby offering a broader understanding of this mathematical phenomenon.

By bridging the gap between theory and computation, this preprint serves as both a practical and instructional resource. It enables readers to test the results of our research independently and explore the behavior of tetration's least significant digits across a wide range of bases.

2. Definitions

In this section, given $a \in \mathbb{N} - \{0, 1\}$ and $b \in \mathbb{N} - \{0\}$ (possibly such that a is not a multiple of 10), we provide the definitions of congruence speed, constant congruence speed, phase shift, modular phase shift, asymptotic phase shift, and stable digits of ${}^b a := \begin{cases} a & \text{if } b = 1 \\ a({}^{b-1}a) & \text{if } b \geq 2 \end{cases}$.

Indeed, assuming the standard decimal numeral system, the integer tetration ${}^b a$ is characterized by the following properties.

Definition 2.1. Let $a \in \mathbb{N} - \{0, 1\}$ be such that a is not a multiple of 10. Let $v_2(a)$ and $v_5(a)$ indicate the 2-adic and the 5-adic valuation of a (respectively). Then, nonnegative integer $\tilde{v}(a)$ is as follows:

$$\tilde{v}(a) = \begin{cases} v_5(a - 1) & \text{if } a \equiv 1 \pmod{5} \\ v_5(a^2 + 1) & \text{if } a \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{5} \\ v_5(a + 1) & \text{if } a \equiv 4 \pmod{5} \\ v_2(a^2 - 1) - 1 & \text{if } a \equiv 5 \pmod{5} \\ 1 & \text{if } a \equiv 0 \pmod{5} \end{cases}.$$

Definition 2.2. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and assume that $a \in \mathbb{N} - \{0, 1\}$ is not a multiple of 10. Then, given ${}^{b-1}a \equiv {}^b a \pmod{10^n}$ and ${}^{b-1}a \not\equiv {}^b a \pmod{10^{n+1}}$, for all $b > a$, $V(a, b)$ returns the strictly positive integer such that ${}^b a \equiv {}^{b+1}a \pmod{10^{n+V(a,b)}}$ and ${}^b a \not\equiv {}^{b+1}a \pmod{10^{n+V(a,b)+1}}$, and we define $V(a, b)$ as the “congruence speed” of the base a at the given height of its hyperexponent b . Furthermore, let $\tilde{b} \geq \tilde{v}(a) + 2$ (where $\tilde{v}(a)$ is stated in Definition 2.1) so that we define as “constant congruence speed” of a , the positive integer $V(a) := V(a, \tilde{b})$.

Definition 2.3. We define as “phase shift” (PS) of a at height b (i.e., $\text{PS}(a, b)$) the congruence class modulo 10 of the difference between the rightmost non stable digit of ${}^b a$, say the d -th digit counting from right to left, and the d -th rightmost digit of ${}^{b+1}a$ (see [7], Definition 3.2). Furthermore, we call “modular phase shift” (MPS) of a the cycle of the 4, 2, or 1 distinct phase shifts of a at heights $\tilde{v}(a) + 2$, $\tilde{v}(a) + 3$, $\tilde{v}(a) + 4$, and $\tilde{v}(a) + 5$ (i.e., one figure numbers belonging to the set $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$).

Definition 2.4. For any $a, b \in \mathbb{N}$, we call “stable digits” all the least significant digits of ${}^b a$ that are equal to the corresponding least significant digits of ${}^{b+2}a$ (e.g., if $a = 3 = b$ is given, then we have ${}^3 3 = 7625597484987$ and ${}^5 3 \equiv {}^3 3 \pmod{10^2} \wedge {}^5 3 \not\equiv {}^3 3 \pmod{10^3}$ so that only the last two digits of ${}^3 3$ are stable digits).

Definition 2.5. Let $\bar{b} := \bar{b}(a)$ the minimum hyperexponent of the given tetration base a such as its congruence speed is constant (for any integer hyperexponent $b \geq \bar{b}$). Then, we define as “asymptotic phase shift” (APS) of a the cycle of the 4, 2, or 1 distinct phase shifts of a at heights $\bar{b}$, $\bar{b} + 1$, $\bar{b} + 2$, and $\bar{b} + 3$ (see [7], Definition 3.2).

In general, as long as $a, b \in \mathbb{N} - \{0, 1\}$ and $b > 2$ if and only if $a = 5$, we note that the congruence speed of a at height b corresponds to the number of the new rightmost digits of a that are stable by moving from ${}^b a$ to ${}^{b+1}a$.

Remark 1. Since, $\tilde{\nu}(a) + 2 \geq \bar{b}$ (see Definitions 2.1 and 2.5) holds for each $a \in \mathbb{N} - \{0, 1\}$, a sufficient but not necessary condition for the constancy of the congruence speed of ${}^b a$ is given by $b \geq \tilde{b}$ (see Definition 2.2).

3. Python programs

Although using a fixed Python compiler is the most reliable option, Programs I to XII have been made accessible for online execution through [Google Colab](#) or [Programiz](#). Each subsection begins with a link to the corresponding Google Colab program, allowing users to run the code directly without needing to copy and paste it. For those who prefer not to log in to Google Colab, the provided links give access to properly formatted codes that can be copied and pasted into the `main.py` page of the Programiz online compiler, available at: <https://www.programiz.com/python-programming/online-compiler/>.

I. The 160 least-significant digits of ${}^b a$.

Run **Program I** directly through Google Colab:

<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1QDOHwyzIqmCr2oqGQT7C6ApB-GZBmPaR?usp=sharing>.

The following Python code calculates and displays the last 160 digits of any input tetration ${}^b a$, for $b = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 20$. For bases a not divisible by 10, the code provides a simple way to explore the recurrence properties in the least significant digits of ${}^b a$, highlighting both the growth in the frozen digits and the sequence of the rightmost non-stable digit as b increases. While the program also works for inputs a that are multiples of 10, the output does not include a sufficient number of digits to fully illustrate the growth rate of frozen digits or the sequence of rightmost non-stable digits at heights $b = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 20$.

```
def last_160_digits_tetration(a):
    """
    Calculates the last 160 digits of the tetration of height 20 for the base
    'a'.

    :param a: Positive integer greater than 1, base of the tetration
    :return: A list containing the last 160 digits of a, a^a, a^(a^a), ...,
    a^^20
    """
    # Modulo to obtain the last 160 digits
    mod = 10 ** 160

    # List to store the results of each tetration level
    tetration = []

    # Add the base number 'a' as the first element (n=1)
    tetration.append(a)

    # Start with the base value for the exponent
    exponent = a
```


6

37757675280045435370801001687831308873309536442788236640244722871739548679315741
79956666830745951284291629677133594022509953076634216229078036010220183482803349

7

96460294196322305832078088712722684165896333240523705470718832960116027187763503
41775267999881571618419191147935166372722448856483410846769061134928183482803349

8

2999526722206894836023455986425316891721685107161510567153421544010827463834020
01839197311658399889427326909792921436970350102122535589870198448128183482803349

9

87346070013885535720225669756128917934373431553129187552221642749853082374643746
92136305526655988269481658370807301694454908793892067542373520728128183482803349

10

40851409052604753206429445843491928752533263742756448713130377329677625413718522
04826538019330367837806713504630073972449462093704347044868732728128183482803349

11

95921331591528537368751990149011080413820490691003459238624443297388305323179227
54194615586704559913686917470702075281518116615629029713723532728128183482803349

12

82003621076453197000997351546663837407302980768330401689085445064492769774979849
61358521462486531295730084654696428599128905898896936638643532728128183482803349

13

93718617454155821470863051900790521324280663029894519704290560206636689465336772
36731885119739267325703046493545352916501279974766202306643532728128183482803349

14

08765790668835651524438169891833095853766626206730235717431855603343934383785565
02389064760792796080787578856841288482804036593511499506643532728128183482803349

15

73462499001140820751082916223532289091642629750701955486953015584124585337414442
83707239464205560343097687419352082441283582081667379506643532728128183482803349

16

85453744713204330499493206116545544779720162419810558087157515015436143752930471
74962833680469969809776748175424184875887737066319379506643532728128183482803349

17

85087062895067875491526534094734375093107589404095607892039047083603448825945947
48154136908866144329604621433815021129502834097119379506643532728128183482803349

18

38720707118333828333162644899972247809969694850647231908886658996122022824417569
89701228369576851837936481479636304738132989417119379506643532728128183482803349

19

45735295804994077414287287946784250249624103120189363161995300887451508577873177
97977399259122735296596950460346411321574817417119379506643532728128183482803349

20

66371708504391260680853217441243765810966876805096513502058726787697095526551321
32383245354720695477019885322382545080936017417119379506643532728128183482803349

II. Constant congruence speed of any nonnegative integer a which is not a multiple of 10 (by Equation (3) of [5]).

Run Program II directly through Google Colab:

<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1k8wAY5pR1lHOzG4Y5YBYAaq16pLyTPG?usp=sharing>.

```
# Helper functions to calculate 2-adic and 5-adic valuations
def v2(n):
    count = 0
    while n % 2 == 0 and n > 0:
```

```

        n //= 2
        count += 1
    return count

def v5(n):
    count = 0
    while n % 5 == 0 and n > 0:
        n //= 5
        count += 1
    return count

# Function to calculate V(a) based on the given rules
def calculate_congruence_speed():
    # Step 1: Prompt the user for input
    print("Write an integer tetration base 'a' (a ≥ 0).")
    print("Note: If a = 0 or a = 1, V(a) = 0.")
    print("If a > 0 and a is a multiple of 10, the constant congruence speed is
undefined.")

    # Try to get valid integer input
    try:
        a = int(input("Enter the value of 'a': "))
    except ValueError:
        print("Invalid input: please write a nonnegative integer!")
        return

    # Step 2: Handle special cases
    if a < 0:
        print("Invalid input: please write a nonnegative integer!")
        return
    if a == 0 or a == 1:
        print(f"V({a}) = 0")
        return
    if a > 0 and a % 10 == 0:
        print(f"There does not exist any hyperexponent such that the congruence
speed of '{a}' is constant as '{a}' is congruent to 0 modulo 10.")
        return

    # Step 3: Calculate V(a) for valid cases
    mod_20 = a % 20
    mod_10 = a % 10

    if mod_20 == 1:
        result = min(v2(a - 1), v5(a - 1))
    elif mod_20 == 11:
        result = min(v2(a + 1), v5(a - 1))
    elif mod_10 in {2, 8}:
        result = v5(a ** 2 + 1)
    elif mod_20 in {3, 7}:
        result = min(v2(a + 1), v5(a ** 2 + 1))
    elif mod_20 in {13, 17}:
        result = min(v2(a - 1), v5(a ** 2 + 1))
    elif mod_10 == 4:
        result = v5(a + 1)
    elif mod_20 == 5:
        result = v2(a - 1)
    elif mod_20 == 15:
        result = v2(a + 1)
    elif mod_10 == 6:
        result = v5(a - 1)
    elif mod_20 == 9:
        result = min(v2(a - 1), v5(a + 1))
    elif mod_20 == 19:

```

```

        result = min(v2(a + 1), v5(a + 1))
    else:
        print("The base 'a' does not correspond to any supported case.")
        return

    # Step 4: Output the constant congruence speed V(a)
    print(f"V({a}) = {result}")

# Run the program
calculate_congruence_speed()

```

Program II uses the fastest known formula (Equation (3) from Corollary 2.2 of [5]) to calculate the exact value of the constant congruence speed, $V(a)$, of any input tetration base $a \geq 0$ (not a multiple of 10).

Input: “Write an integer tetration base 'a' ($a \geq 0$).

If $a > 0$ and a is a multiple of 10, the congruence speed does not exist.

Enter the value of 'a':”. Here you type the chosen tetration base (e.g., 807).

In our example, the output is:

$V(807) = 3$.

III. Modular phase shift of the tetration base n written by juxtaposing its representative congruence classes modulo 10 taken by starting from height $\tilde{v}(n) + 2$ to height $\tilde{v}(n) + 5$, and $a(n) = -1$ if n is a multiple of 10 (sequence A376446 of the OEIS [2]).

Run **Program III** directly through Google Colab:

<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1ho3Hpbud7Ja3Ce9WCNaZnwHEjTHm9eVb?usp=sharing>.

```

# Function to calculate the p-adic valuation
def p_adic_valuation(n, p):
    count = 0
    while n % p == 0 and n != 0:
        n //= p
        count += 1
    return count

# Function to calculate tetration (tower of powers)
def tetration(base, height, last_digits=500):
    results = [base]
    for n in range(1, height):
        # Compute only the last 'last_digits' digits
        result = pow(base, results[-1], 10**last_digits)
        results.append(result)
    return results

# Function to find the first non-zero difference and compute modulo 10
def find_difference_mod_10(tetrations):
    differences = []
    for n in range(len(tetrations) - 1):
        string_n = str(tetrations[n]).zfill(500) # Pad with zeros if needed
        string_n_plus_1 = str(tetrations[n + 1]).zfill(500)

```

```

    # Find the first difference starting from the rightmost digit
    for i in range(499, -1, -1): # From right to left
        if string_n[i] != string_n_plus_1[i]:
            difference = (int(string_n[i]) - int(string_n_plus_1[i])) % 10
            differences.append(difference)
            break
    return differences

# Function to determine the first hyperexponent based on modulo 5 congruences
def calculate_initial_exponent(a):
    mod_5 = a % 5
    if mod_5 == 1:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a - 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    elif mod_5 in [2, 3]:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a**2 + 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    elif mod_5 == 4:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a + 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    else:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a**2 - 1, 2)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 1
    return initial_exponent

# Main logic
try:
    # Input validation
    a = int(input("Enter a positive integer greater than 1: "))
    if a % 10 == 0:
        print(-1)
    elif a <= 1:
        raise ValueError("The number must be greater than 1.")
    else:
        # Calculate the initial exponent based on modulo 5 congruence
        initial_exponent = calculate_initial_exponent(a)

        # Generate tetrations for 30 iterations and the last 500 digits
        tetrations = tetration(a, 30, last_digits=500)

        # Find the modulo 10 differences for the 4 required iterations
        mod_10_differences = find_difference_mod_10(tetrations[initial_exponent
- 1:initial_exponent + 4])

        # Optimization of the output
        if mod_10_differences[:2] == mod_10_differences[2:]:
            mod_10_differences = mod_10_differences[:2]
        if len(set(mod_10_differences)) == 1:
            mod_10_differences = [mod_10_differences[0]]

        # Convert the list of differences into a string without brackets or
commas
        result_str = ''.join(map(str, mod_10_differences))

        # Print the optimized result
        print(f"a({a}) = {result_str}")
except Exception as e:
    print(f"ERROR!\n{e}")

```

Program III gives the *modular phase shifts* (MPSs) of the input tetration base a if its last digit is not equal to 0, otherwise it returns the value -1 . The modular phase shift is written here as a 1, 2, or

4 digits number (e.g., 6842 instead of [6, 8, 4, 2]), thus omitting square brackets, spaces, and commas (see [2], sequences A376446 and A378421).

Input: “Enter a positive integer greater than 1:” Here you type the chosen tetration base (e.g., 73).

In our example, the output is:

$a(73) = 6842$.

IV. Modular phase shifts (MPSs) of the tetration bases congruent to 2, 4, 6, 8 (mod 10) belonging to a given interval. It considers the phase shifts of each tetration base as above which is in the given range from height $\tilde{v}(a) + 2$ to height $\tilde{v}(a) + 5$ (e.g., $MPS(24) = 8$ since the phase shift of 24 at heights $\tilde{v}(a) + 2$, $\tilde{v}(a) + 3$, $\tilde{v}(a) + 4$, and $\tilde{v}(a) + 5$ is always equal to 8).

Run **Program IV** directly through Google Colab:

https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1mrMIGAn8uV3vhvgwjzFXbi_KatBx54-G?usp=sharing.

```
# Function to calculate the p-adic valuation
def p_adic_valuation(n, p):
    count = 0
    while n % p == 0 and n != 0:
        n //= p
        count += 1
    return count

# Function to calculate tetration (tower of powers)
def tetration(base, height, last_digits=500):
    results = [base]

    for n in range(1, height):
        result = pow(base, results[-1], 10**last_digits) # Only the last
last_digits digits
        results.append(result)

    return results

# Function to find the first non-zero difference and compute modulo 10
def find_difference_mod_10(tetrations):
    differences = []

    for n in range(len(tetrations) - 1):
        string_n = str(tetrations[n]).zfill(500) # Pad with zeros if needed
        string_n_plus_1 = str(tetrations[n+1]).zfill(500)

        # Find the first difference starting from the rightmost digit
        for i in range(499, -1, -1): # From right to left
            if string_n[i] != string_n_plus_1[i]:
                difference = (int(string_n[i]) - int(string_n_plus_1[i])) % 10
                differences.append(difference)
                break

    return differences
```

```

# Function to determine the first hyperexponent based on modulo 5 congruences
def calculate_initial_exponent(a):
    mod_5 = a % 5
    if mod_5 == 1:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a - 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    elif mod_5 in [2, 3]:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a**2 + 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    elif mod_5 == 4:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a + 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    else:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a**2 - 1, 2)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 1
    return initial_exponent

# Main logic
try:
    start = int(input("Enter the start of the range (positive integer greater
than 1): "))
    end = int(input("Enter the end of the range (positive integer greater than
1): "))

    if start <= 1 or end <= 1:
        raise ValueError("Both numbers must be greater than 1.")

    valid_integers = [a for a in range(start, end + 1) if str(a)[-1] in ['2',
'4', '6', '8']]

    if not valid_integers:
        raise ValueError("No valid integers in the specified range end with 2,
4, 6, or 8.")

    results = {}

    for a in valid_integers:
        # Calculate the initial exponent based on modulo 5 congruence
        initial_exponent = calculate_initial_exponent(a)

        # Generate tetrations for 30 iterations and the last 500 digits
        tetrations = tetration(a, 30, last_digits=500)

        # Find the modulo 10 differences for the 4 required iterations
        mod_10_differences = find_difference_mod_10(tetrations[initial_exponent-
1:initial_exponent+4])

        # Optimization of the output
        if mod_10_differences[:2] == mod_10_differences[2:]:
            mod_10_differences = mod_10_differences[:2]
        if len(set(mod_10_differences)) == 1:
            mod_10_differences = [mod_10_differences[0]]

        # Store the result in the dictionary
        results[a] = mod_10_differences

    # Print the results for each valid integer
    for a, mod_10_differences in results.items():
        print(f"MPS({a}) = {mod_10_differences}")

except Exception as e:
    print(f"ERROR!\n{e}")

```

Program IV calculates the *modular phase shifts* (MPSs) of the tetration bases whose last digit is 2, 4, 6, or 8 inside a given range.

Step 1: “Enter the start of the range (positive integer greater than 1) :”. Here you can type the smallest integer of your range (e.g., 24).

Step 2: “Enter the end of the range (positive integer greater than 1) :”. Here you can type the biggest integer of your range (e.g., 42).

In our example, the output is as follows:

```
MPS(24) = [8]
MPS(26) = [6, 4]
MPS(28) = [8, 6, 2, 4]
MPS(32) = [2, 6, 8, 4]
MPS(34) = [8, 2]
MPS(36) = [4]
MPS(38) = [2, 8]
MPS(42) = [4, 2, 6, 8].
```

V. Phase shifts of the tetration base a at heights $b = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, 11$.

Run **Program V** directly through Google Colab:

https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1UsL6RZZEs8UXuF_cBHo6qt83hLoMYK7s?usp=sharing.

```
# Function to calculate tetration (power tower)
def tetration(base, height, final_digits=70):
    # The first iteration is just the base
    results = [base]

    for n in range(1, height):
        # Raise the previous result to the power of the base
        result = pow(base, results[-1], 10**final_digits) # only the last
final_digits digits
        results.append(result)

    return results

# Function to find the non-zero difference and calculate modulo 10
def find_difference_mod_10(tetrations, initial_height, final_height):
    differences = []

    # Loop to compare tetrations from initial_height to final_height
    for n in range(initial_height, final_height):
        string_n = str(tetrations[n]).zfill(70)
        string_n_plus_1 = str(tetrations[n+1]).zfill(70)

        # Find the first difference starting from the right
        for i in range(69, -1, -1): # from right to left
            if string_n[i] != string_n_plus_1[i]:
                difference = (int(string_n[i]) - int(string_n_plus_1[i])) % 10
                differences.append(difference)
                break

    return differences
```

```

# Main
try:
    a = int(input("Enter a positive integer greater than 1: "))

    if a <= 1:
        raise ValueError("The number must be greater than 1.")

    # Generate tetrations up to height 12
    tetrations = tetration(a, 12)
    print(f"Calculated results: {len(tetrations)} tetrations generated.")

    # Find modulo 10 differences for tetrations from 5 to 11
    differences_mod_10 = find_difference_mod_10(tetrations, 0, 11)

    # Show the final differences
    print(f"Modulo 10 differences: {differences_mod_10}")

except Exception as e:
    print(f"ERROR!\n{e}")

```

Program V gives the phase shifts of the the input tetration base a at heights 1 to 11.

Input: “Enter a positive integer greater than 1:” Here you type the chosen tetration base (e.g., 13).

In our example, the output is:

Calculated results: 12 tetrations generated.
Modulo 10 differences: [6, 2, 4, 8, 6, 2, 4, 8, 6, 2, 4].

VI. Smallest tetration base coprime to 10 which is characterized by the input MPS (see [2], sequence A376446) starting from height $\tilde{v}(a) + 2$ to height $\tilde{v}(a) + 5$.

Run Program VI directly through Google Colab:

<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1x7hWuy8hjAJTcYZuqLtaGEHB1bsUqu2v?usp=sharing>.

```

import math

# Function to calculate the p-adic valuation
def p_adic_valuation(n, p):
    count = 0
    while n % p == 0 and n != 0:
        n //= p
        count += 1
    return count

# Function to calculate tetration (tower of powers) with modulo optimization
def tetration(base, height, last_digits=500):
    results = [base]
    for n in range(1, height):
        result = pow(base, results[-1], 10**last_digits) # Only the last
last_digits digits
        results.append(result)
    return results

```

```

# Function to find the first non-zero difference and compute modulo 10
def find_difference_mod_10(tetrations):
    differences = []
    for n in range(len(tetrations) - 1):
        string_n = str(tetrations[n]).zfill(500) # Pad with zeros if needed
        string_n_plus_1 = str(tetrations[n+1]).zfill(500)

        # Find the first difference starting from the rightmost digit
        for i in range(499, -1, -1): # From right to left
            if string_n[i] != string_n_plus_1[i]:
                difference = (int(string_n[i]) - int(string_n_plus_1[i])) % 10
                differences.append(difference)
                break
    return differences

# Function to determine the first hyperexponent based on modulo 5 congruences
def calculate_initial_exponent(a):
    mod_5 = a % 5
    if mod_5 == 1:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a - 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    elif mod_5 in [2, 3]:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a**2 + 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    elif mod_5 == 4:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a + 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    else:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a**2 - 1, 2)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 1
    return initial_exponent

# Function to calculate the result for a given base 'a'
def calculate_result_for_a(a):
    # Calculate the initial exponent based on modulo 5 congruence
    initial_exponent = calculate_initial_exponent(a)

    # Generate tetrations for 30 iterations and the last 500 digits
    tetrations = tetration(a, 30, last_digits=500)

    # Find the modulo 10 differences for the 4 required iterations
    mod_10_differences = find_difference_mod_10(tetrations[initial_exponent-1:initial_exponent+4])

    # Optimization of the output
    if mod_10_differences[:2] == mod_10_differences[2:]:
        mod_10_differences = mod_10_differences[:2]
    if len(set(mod_10_differences)) == 1:
        mod_10_differences = [mod_10_differences[0]]

    return mod_10_differences

# Function to find the smallest 'a' that matches the target digits
def find_smallest_a(target_digits):
    # Restrict 'a' to be coprime with 10 (i.e., last digit must be 1, 3, 7, or 9)
    a = 1 # Start at 1
    while a <= 10**12: # Search up to 10^12
        if a % 10 not in {1, 3, 7, 9}:
            a += 1
            continue

    # Calculate the result for the current 'a'

```

```

    result_digits = calculate_result_for_a(a)

    # Check if the result matches the target digits
    if result_digits == target_digits:
        return a

    # Increment 'a' by 2 (skip even numbers since they aren't coprime with
10)
    a += 2

    return None # If no match is found

# Main script
if __name__ == "__main__":
    # Input: target digits in brackets (e.g., [5] or [2, 6, 8, 4] or [6, 4])
    input_digits = input("Enter the target digits to search for (e.g., [5] or
[2, 6, 8, 4]): ")

    # Convert the input string into a list of integers
    target_digits = list(map(int, input_digits.strip('[]').split(',')))

    # Find the smallest 'a' that matches the target digits
    smallest_a = find_smallest_a(target_digits)

    # Output the result
    if smallest_a is not None:
        print(f"The smallest value of 'a' that produces {target_digits} is
{smallest_a}.")
    else:
        print("No value of 'a' found that matches the given digits.")

```

Program VI needs a valid modular phase shift as an input (e.g., [1, 9] – see [2] sequence A378421) and returns the smallest tetration base coprime whose last digit belongs to the set {1, 3, 7, 9} which is characterized by the input MPS.

Input: “Enter the target digits to search for (e.g., [5] or [2, 6, 8, 4]) :”. Here you type the chosen tetration base (e.g., [1, 9]).

In our example, the output is (running the code on Google Colab, in December 2024, the execution time for [1, 9] has been 2 min 42 s):

The smallest value of 'a' that produces [1, 9] is 901.

VII. Smallest tetration base a that ends with the last input d digits and that is characterized by any chosen MPS (see [2], sequence A376446) starting from height $\tilde{\nu}(a) + 2$ to height $\tilde{\nu}(a) + 5$.

Run **Program VII** directly through Google Colab:

https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1MgjZfrPObitbU9fLaMN_UwU0n4E-L8gG?usp=sharing.

```

# Function to calculate the p-adic valuation
def p_adic_valuation(n, p):
    count = 0
    while n % p == 0 and n != 0:

```

```

        n //= p
        count += 1
    return count

# Function to calculate tetration (tower of powers)
def tetration(base, height, last_digits=500):
    results = [base]

    for n in range(1, height):
        result = pow(base, results[-1], 10**last_digits) # Only the last
last_digits digits
        results.append(result)

    return results

# Function to find the first non-zero difference and compute modulo 10
def find_difference_mod_10(tetrations):
    differences = []

    for n in range(len(tetrations) - 1):
        string_n = str(tetrations[n]).zfill(500) # Pad with zeros if needed
        string_n_plus_1 = str(tetrations[n+1]).zfill(500)

        # Find the first difference starting from the rightmost digit
        for i in range(499, -1, -1): # From right to left
            if string_n[i] != string_n_plus_1[i]:
                difference = (int(string_n[i]) - int(string_n_plus_1[i])) % 10
                differences.append(difference)
                break

    return differences

# Function to determine the first hyperexponent based on modulo 5 congruences
def calculate_initial_exponent(a):
    mod_5 = a % 5
    if mod_5 == 1:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a - 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    elif mod_5 in [2, 3]:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a**2 + 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    elif mod_5 == 4:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a + 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    else:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a**2 - 1, 2)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 1
    return initial_exponent

# Main logic to find the smallest 'a' that matches a given set of differences
def find_smallest_a_with_digits(target_output, last_digits_of_a, limit=100000):
    target_output = [int(x) for x in target_output] # Convert string input to
list of integers
    last_digits_len = len(last_digits_of_a) # Length of the specified ending
digits

    for a in range(2, limit + 1):
        try:
            # Check if the last digits of 'a' match the specified digits
            if str(a)[-last_digits_len:] == last_digits_of_a:
                # Calculate the initial exponent based on modulo 5 congruence
                initial_exponent = calculate_initial_exponent(a)

```

```

        # Generate tetrations for 30 iterations and the last 500 digits
        tetrations = tetration(a, 30, last_digits=500)

        # Find the modulo 10 differences for the 4 required iterations
        mod_10_differences =
find_difference_mod_10(tetrations[initial_exponent-1:initial_exponent+4])

        # Optimization of the output
        if mod_10_differences[:2] == mod_10_differences[2:]:
            mod_10_differences = mod_10_differences[:2]
        if len(set(mod_10_differences)) == 1:
            mod_10_differences = [mod_10_differences[0]]

        # Compare with target_output
        if mod_10_differences == target_output:
            return a

    except Exception as e:
        continue # Skip the value if any error occurs

    return None # If no value of 'a' is found within the limit

# User input and result
try:
    target_output = input("Enter the target output in the format [5] or [2, 6,
8, 4]: ").strip('[]').split(', ')
    last_digits_of_a = input("Enter the last digits of 'a' you want to search
for: ").strip()
    limit = int(input("Enter the upper limit for 'a' (e.g., 100000): "))

    result = find_smallest_a_with_digits(target_output, last_digits_of_a,
limit=limit)

    if result is not None:
        print(f"The smallest 'a' that produces the output {target_output} with
last digits {last_digits_of_a} is {result}.")
    else:
        print(f"No 'a' found that produces the output {target_output} with last
digits {last_digits_of_a} up to {limit}.")

except Exception as e:
    print(f"ERROR!\n{e}")

```

Program VII finds the smallest tetration base ending with the last $d \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ input digits and which is characterized by the input (valid) MPS.

Step 1: “Enter the target output in the format [5] or [2, 6, 8, 4]:”. Here you can type the smallest integer of your range (e.g., [1, 9]).

Step 2: “Enter the last digits of 'a' you want to search for:”. Here you have to type a number of $d \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ digits which is congruent modulo 10^d to the tetration base you aim to find, including 0s to the left of the leftmost nonzero digit you have entered (e.g., type 01 to restrict the search to only the values of a ending with 01).

Step 3: “Enter the upper limit for 'a' (e.g., 100000):”. Here you need to write the maximum value (up to 100000) that the program will check in order to say if there is a valid tetration base which is not greater than it (e.g., enter 2000 to see if there is a solution in the interval [2, 2000]).

In our example, the output is as follows:

The smallest 'a' that produces the output ['1', '9'] with last digits 01 is 901.

VIII. Phase shifts of the tetration base a at heights $b = \tilde{v}(a) + 2, \tilde{v}(a) + 3, \dots, \tilde{v}(a) + 20$.

Run **Program VIII** directly through Google Colab:

<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1SM-PcOhPjqQltnuzu-ofaRjlnCZjoq8?usp=sharing>.

```
# Function to calculate the p-adic valuation
def p_adic_valuation(n, p):
    count = 0
    while n % p == 0 and n != 0:
        n //= p
        count += 1
    return count

# Function to calculate tetration (tower of powers)
def tetration(base, height, last_digits=2000):
    results = [base]

    for n in range(1, height):
        result = pow(base, results[-1], 10**last_digits) # Only the last
last_digits digits
        results.append(result)

    return results

# Function to find the first non-zero difference and compute modulo 10
def find_difference_mod_10(tetrations):
    differences = []

    for n in range(len(tetrations) - 1):
        string_n = str(tetrations[n]).zfill(2000) # Pad with zeros if needed
        string_n_plus_1 = str(tetrations[n+1]).zfill(2000)

        # Find the first difference starting from the rightmost digit
        for i in range(1999, -1, -1): # From right to left
            if string_n[i] != string_n_plus_1[i]:
                difference = (int(string_n[i]) - int(string_n_plus_1[i])) % 10
                differences.append(difference)
                break

    return differences

# Function to determine the first hyperexponent based on modulo 5 congruences
def calculate_initial_exponent(a):
    mod_5 = a % 5
    if mod_5 == 1:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a - 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    elif mod_5 in [2, 3]:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a**2 + 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    elif mod_5 == 4:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a + 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    else:
```

```

        valuation = p_adic_valuation(a**2 - 1, 2)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 1
    return initial_exponent

# Main logic
try:
    a = int(input("Enter a positive integer greater than 1: "))

    if a <= 1:
        raise ValueError("The number must be greater than 1.")

    # Calculate the initial exponent based on modulo 5 congruence
    initial_exponent = calculate_initial_exponent(a)

    # Generate tetrations for 20 iterations and the last 2000 digits
    tetrations = tetration(a, 20, last_digits=2000)

    # Find the modulo 10 differences for the 20 required iterations
    mod_10_differences = find_difference_mod_10(tetrations[initial_exponent-
1:initial_exponent+20])

    # Print the optimized result in square brackets
    print(f"MPS({a}) = {mod_10_differences}")

except Exception as e:
    print(f"ERROR!\n{e}")

```

Program VIII is quite unuseful by knowing the fact that, for any integer $m \geq 2$, the phase shift of $\tilde{v}(a) + m$ only depends on the congruence modulo 4 of m (e.g., if $m = 8007$, then the PS of any given a at height 8007 is equal to the PS of a at height 3 since $8007 \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$). Basically, the program returns all the phase shifts of the input tetration base a at heights $\tilde{v}(a) + 2$, $\tilde{v}(a) + 3$, $\tilde{v}(a) + 4$, ..., up to $\tilde{v}(a) + 20$.

Input: "Enter a positive integer greater than 1:" Here you type the chosen tetration base (e.g., 49).

In our example, the output is:

MPS(49) = [2, 6, 8, 4, 2, 6, 8, 4, 2, 6, 8, 4, 2, 6, 8, 4].

IX. Phase shift of the tetration base $a_{j=1,2,\dots,n}$ at height a_j (see [2], sequence A376883), up to the input maximum value n (maximum entry allowed $n = 100$ – see the OEIS sequences A376883 and A377124).

Run **Program** directly through Google Colab:

<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/18DluzGknSU2YgVclY1E4cXD4aQuN5rct?usp=sharing>.

```

def tetration_modulo(base, height, final_digits=500):
    results = [base]
    for _ in range(1, height):
        result = pow(base, results[-1], 10**final_digits)
        results.append(result)
    return results

def find_non_stable_mod_10(tetrations, height):
    string_a = str(tetrations[height]).zfill(500)

```

```

string_a_plus_1 = str(tetrations[height + 1]).zfill(500)
for i in range(499, -1, -1):
    if string_a[i] != string_a_plus_1[i]:
        difference = (int(string_a[i]) - int(string_a_plus_1[i])) % 10
        return difference
return "Stable"
try:
a = int(input("Write the maximum value of a (from 2 to 100): "))
if a < 2 or a > 100:
    raise ValueError("Please, insert an integer between 2 and 100")
for a in range(2, a + 1):
    if a % 10 == 0:
        print(f"PS({a}) = A377124({a // 10})")
    else:
        tetrations = tetration_modulo(a, a + 1)
        tetrations.append(pow(a, tetrations[-1], 10**500))
        difference = find_non_stable_mod_10(tetrations, a - 1)
        if difference == "Stable":
            print(f"PS({a}) = Stable")
        else:
            print(f"PS({a}) = {difference}")
except Exception as e:
    print(f"ERROR!\a{e}")

```

Program IX gives the phase shift of any (positive) tetration base $a > 1$ at height a up to the inputex maximum value of b (from 2 to 100).

Input: "Write the maximum value of n (from 2 to 100):" Here you type the maximum tetration base that the program will consider (e.g., 89).

In our example, the output is:

```

PS(2) = 8
PS(3) = 6
PS(4) = 4
PS(5) = 5
PS(6) = 8
PS(7) = 6
PS(8) = 4
PS(9) = 2
PS(10) = A377124(1)
PS(11) = 4
PS(12) = 4
PS(13) = 6
PS(14) = 8
PS(15) = 5
PS(16) = 6
PS(17) = 4
PS(18) = 8
PS(19) = 6
PS(20) = A377124(2)
PS(21) = 6
PS(22) = 8
PS(23) = 4
PS(24) = 8
PS(25) = 5
PS(26) = 6
PS(27) = 6
PS(28) = 6
PS(29) = 6
PS(30) = A377124(3)
PS(31) = 4

```

PS (32) = 2
PS (33) = 2
PS (34) = 2
PS (35) = 5
PS (36) = 4
PS (37) = 2
PS (38) = 8
PS (39) = 8
PS (40) = A377124 (4)
PS (41) = 4
PS (42) = 8
PS (43) = 6
PS (44) = 6
PS (45) = 5
PS (46) = 2
PS (47) = 4
PS (48) = 2
PS (49) = 6
PS (50) = A377124 (5)
PS (51) = 5
PS (52) = 6
PS (53) = 8
PS (54) = 6
PS (55) = 5
PS (56) = 2
PS (57) = 2
PS (58) = 8
PS (59) = 2
PS (60) = A377124 (6)
PS (61) = 4
PS (62) = 8
PS (63) = 4
PS (64) = 8
PS (65) = 5
PS (66) = 6
PS (67) = 4
PS (68) = 4
PS (69) = 4
PS (70) = A377124 (7)
PS (71) = 4
PS (72) = 8
PS (73) = 4
PS (74) = 4
PS (75) = 5
PS (76) = 8
PS (77) = 8
PS (78) = 8
PS (79) = 4
PS (80) = A377124 (8)
PS (81) = 6
PS (82) = 8
PS (83) = 6
PS (84) = 2
PS (85) = 5
PS (86) = 4
PS (87) = 6
PS (88) = 8
PS (89) = 8

[Where A377124(n) indicates the n -th element of the OEIS sequence A377124.]

X. Number of distinct entries that characterize the asymptotic phase shift and the modular phase shift of the input tetration base (see [2], sequence A377126).

Run **Program X** directly through Google Colab:

<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1XXraDAwu3in0lcKnVeKNrAU1zSVoY1JS?usp=sharing>.

```
def p_adic_valuation(n, p):
    count = 0
    while n % p == 0 and n != 0:
        n //= p
        count += 1
    return count

def tetration(base, height, last_digits=500):
    results = [base]
    for n in range(1, height):
        result = pow(base, results[-1], 10**last_digits)
        results.append(result)
    return results

def find_difference_mod_10(tetrations):
    differences = []
    for n in range(len(tetrations) - 1):
        string_n = str(tetrations[n]).zfill(500)
        string_n_plus_1 = str(tetrations[n+1]).zfill(500)
        for i in range(499, -1, -1):
            if string_n[i] != string_n_plus_1[i]:
                difference = (int(string_n[i]) - int(string_n_plus_1[i])) % 10
                differences.append(difference)
                break
    return differences

def calculate_initial_exponent(n):
    mod_5 = n % 5
    if mod_5 == 1:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(n - 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    elif mod_5 in [2, 3]:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(n**2 + 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    elif mod_5 == 4:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(n + 1, 5)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 2
    else:
        valuation = p_adic_valuation(n**2 - 1, 2)
        initial_exponent = valuation + 1
    return initial_exponent

try:
    n = int(input("Write a tetration base (between 2 and 100): "))
    if n < 2 or n > 100:
        raise ValueError("The base must be between 2 and 100.")
    if n % 10 == 0:
        print("-1 (since the asymptotic phase shift is only defined for n not a
multiple of 10)")
    else:
        initial_exponent = calculate_initial_exponent(n)
        tetrations = tetration(n, 30, last_digits=500)
        mod_10_differences = find_difference_mod_10(tetrations[initial_exponent-
1:initial_exponent+4])
        if mod_10_differences[:2] == mod_10_differences[2:]:
            mod_10_differences = mod_10_differences[:2]
```

```

        if len(set(mod_10_differences)) == 1:
            mod_10_differences = [mod_10_differences[0]]
            result_str = ''.join(map(str, mod_10_differences))
            print(f"Number of digits of the asymptotic phase shift of n:
{len(result_str)}")
except Exception as e:
    print(f"ERROR!\n{e}")

```

Program X gives the number of distinct digits of the asymptotic phase shift (and also the number of digits characterizing the modular phase shift) of the input tetration base $a > 1$ not a multiple of 10.

Input: “Write a tetration base (between 2 and 100):” Here you type the chosen tetration base (e.g., 28 – see [2], sequences A376842 and A378419).

In our example, the output is:

Number of digits of the asymptotic phase shift of n: 4.

XI. Constant congruence speed of $0, 1, 2, \dots, n - 1$ for any chosen positive integer n (see [2], sequence A373387).

Run Program XI directly through Google Colab:

https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1dz_NfvFgQcVt3VpfmHVbAtet6feIE4d-?usp=sharing.

```

# Helper functions to calculate 2-adic and 5-adic valuations
def v2(n):
    count = 0
    while n % 2 == 0 and n > 0:
        n //= 2
        count += 1
    return count

def v5(n):
    count = 0
    while n % 5 == 0 and n > 0:
        n //= 5
        count += 1
    return count

# Function to calculate V(a) for valid cases
def V(a):
    mod_20 = a % 20
    mod_10 = a % 10

    if mod_20 == 1:
        return min(v2(a - 1), v5(a - 1))
    elif mod_20 == 11:
        return min(v2(a + 1), v5(a - 1))
    elif mod_10 in {2, 8}:
        return v5(a ** 2 + 1)
    elif mod_20 in {3, 7}:
        return min(v2(a + 1), v5(a ** 2 + 1))
    elif mod_20 in {13, 17}:
        return min(v2(a - 1), v5(a ** 2 + 1))
    elif mod_10 == 4:

```


1, 1, 1, 3, 1, 2, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 2, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2, 1,
1, 1, -1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 3, 1, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 5, 1, 1, 1, 2, -1, 2, 1, 1,
1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 3, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 6, 2, 1, 1, 1,
-1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 3, 1, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 2, -1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 2,
1, 2, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 3, 1, 1, 2, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 4, 4, 4, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1,
2, 1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 2, -1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 4, 1, 2,
1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 3, 1, 1, 2, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 3, 1,
1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 3, 1, 1, 1, 2, -1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 6, 1, 2, 1, 1,
-1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 2, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 5,
1, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 3, 1, 1, 1, 2, -1, 3, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 1, -1, 1,
1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 2, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 3, 2, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 4, 1, 1,
1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 2, -1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 3, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1,
1, 4, 1, 1, 3, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 3, 2, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 1,
-1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 2, -1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 3, 1, 2, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 5,
1, 1, 2, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 3, 2, 3, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1,
1, 2, 1, 7, 1, 1, 1, 2, -1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 3, 1, 2, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 1,
2, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 3, 1, 1, 3, 1, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 3,
1, 4, 1, 1, 1, 2, -1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 2, 1,
-1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 4, 2, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 3, 1, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 2,
1, 1, 1, 3, -1, 3, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 3, 1, 1, 2, 1, -1, 1,
1, 1, 2, 10, 2

XII. A fairly random tetration base $a := a(c)$ that is (exactly) a perfect c -th power of an integer and such that its constant congruence speed is exactly equal to c , for any input integer $c \geq 2$ (see [8]).

Run **Program XII** directly through Google Colab:

<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1aUhDuKgmMNiyFnWJWFAd8p5mPaW9Sduq?usp=sharing>.

```
import random

def calculate_v2(n):
    """Calculate the 2-adic valuation of n."""
    count = 0
    while n % 2 == 0 and n > 0:
        n //= 2
        count += 1
    return count

def calculate_v5(n):
    """Calculate the 5-adic valuation of n."""
    count = 0
    while n % 5 == 0 and n > 0:
        n //= 5
        count += 1
    return count

def calculate_congruence_speed(a):
    """Calculate the constant congruence speed V(a)."""
    if a == 0 or a == 1:
        return 0
    if a % 10 == 0:
        return None # The constant congruence speed is undefined for multiples
of 10

    mod_20 = a % 20
```

```

mod_10 = a % 10

if mod_20 == 1:
    return min(calculate_v2(a - 1), calculate_v5(a - 1))
elif mod_20 == 11:
    return min(calculate_v2(a + 1), calculate_v5(a - 1))
elif mod_10 in {2, 8}:
    return calculate_v5(a ** 2 + 1)
elif mod_20 in {3, 7}:
    return min(calculate_v2(a + 1), calculate_v5(a ** 2 + 1))
elif mod_20 in {13, 17}:
    return min(calculate_v2(a - 1), calculate_v5(a ** 2 + 1))
elif mod_10 == 4:
    return calculate_v5(a + 1)
elif mod_20 == 5:
    return calculate_v2(a - 1)
elif mod_20 == 15:
    return calculate_v2(a + 1)
elif mod_10 == 6:
    return calculate_v5(a - 1)
elif mod_20 == 9:
    return min(calculate_v2(a - 1), calculate_v5(a + 1))
elif mod_20 == 19:
    return min(calculate_v2(a + 1), calculate_v5(a + 1))
else:
    return None # Unsupported case

def main():
    try:
        c = int(input("Enter a positive integer c (c >= 2): "))
        if c < 2:
            print("The value of c must be at least 2.")
            return

        v2_c = calculate_v2(c)
        v5_c = calculate_v5(c)
        min_v = min(v2_c, v5_c)

        k = random.randint(1, 100)
        base = (10 ** (k + c) + 10 ** (c - min_v) + 1) ** c

        print(f"A random tetration base that is exactly a {c}-th perfect power
and whose constant congruence speed is also equal to {c} is (10^{k+c} + 10^{c-
min_v} + 1)^{c}.")
        print(f"\n[The constant congruence speed of (10^{k+c} + 10^{c-min_v} +
1)^{c} is equal to {c} since it follows from Theorem 2 of Rip\u00e0, M., 'On the
relation between perfect powers and tetration frozen digits', Journal of
AppliedMath (eISSN: 2972-4805), Vol. 2 (2024), No. 5, 1771.]")
        print(f"\nNow calculating the constant congruence speed of the base
(10^{k+c} + 10^{c-min_v} + 1)^{c} for independent verification:")

        congruence_speed = calculate_congruence_speed(base)
        if congruence_speed is None:
            print(f"V((10^{k+c} + 10^{c-min_v} + 1)^{c}) is undefined as the base
is a multiple of 10.")
        else:
            print(f"V((10^{k+c} + 10^{c-min_v} + 1)^{c}) = {congruence_speed}.")
    except ValueError:
        print("Invalid input: please enter a valid positive integer.")

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()

```

Program XII asks to input a positive integer $c > 1$ and returns a random tetration base, say $\tilde{a}^c$ (by taking it from a set of 100 valid solutions), which is exactly a c -th perfect power and that is also characterized by a constant congruence speed of exactly c .

[Here the program uses Theorem 2 of Reference [8] by taking $c := t$ from the general equation $V\left(\left(10^{k+t} + 10^{t-\min\{v_5(c), v_2(c)\}} + 1\right)^c\right) = t$ ($k, c, t \in \mathbb{N} : t > \min\{v_5(c), v_2(c)\} + 1$).]

Then, the program automatically runs a verification test by independently calculating the value of the constant congruence speed of the printed $\tilde{a}^c$ (say), and finally writes the result of this test as $V(\tilde{a}^c) = \dots$ so that we can directly confirm that $V(\tilde{a}^c) = c$ is actually true.

Input: “Enter a positive integer c ($c \geq 2$):” Here you type the chosen degree of the perfect power you are looking for (e.g., 179).

In our example, the output is:

Enter a positive integer c ($c \geq 2$): 179

A random tetration base that is exactly a 179-th perfect power and whose constant congruence speed is also equal to 179 is $(10^{260} + 10^{179} + 1)^{179}$.

[The constant congruence speed of $(10^{260} + 10^{179} + 1)^{179}$ is equal to 179 since it follows from Theorem 2 of Ripà, M., 'On the relation between perfect powers and tetration frozen digits', Journal of AppliedMath (eISSN: 2972-4805), Vol. 2 (2024), No. 5, 1771.]

Now calculating the constant congruence speed of the base $(10^{260} + 10^{179} + 1)^{179}$ for independent verification:

$V((10^{260} + 10^{179} + 1)^{179}) = 179$.

Which confirms that the outputted tetration base $(10^{260} + 10^{179} + 1)^{179}$ is a 179-th perfect power of an integer whose constant congruence speed is also equal to 179 (we note that, in this case, the program has randomly picked an additive constant $k = 260 - 179 = 81$ from the set $\{1, 2, 3, \dots, 99, 100\}$ since $V(10^{180} + 10^{179} + 1)^{179} = V(10^{181} + 10^{179} + 1)^{179} = \dots$).

4. Conclusion

We have provided twelve Python programs to enable readers to test and verify our published results on the congruence speed and phase shift of integer tetration bases. These programs were developed collaboratively with the assistance of OpenAI’s ChatGPT, using equations and formulae from our previously published works (see [4]–[6]).

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(Concerned with sequences [A373387](#), [A376446](#), [A376883](#), [A377124](#), [A377126](#), [A378419](#), and [A378421](#).)